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The first records of *Tephritis hurvitz* (Diptera: Tephritidae) in mainland Ukraine, with notes on its distribution and biology

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Korneyev, S. V., Volovnik, S. V. & Korneyev, V. A. The first records of *Tephritis hurvitz* (Diptera: Tephritidae) in mainland Ukraine, with notes on its distribution and biology. — *Tephritis hurvitz* Freidberg, 1981 is one of few gall-formers in the genus *Tephritis* known to induce stem swellings below flower heads of *Tragopogon* and *Scorzonera* (Asteraceae). It occurs in steppes from eastern Qazaqstan to Israel (Golan Heights) and Ukraine. Previously known only from Crimean Peninsula, it was recently found to occur in the mainland Ukraine. Data on distribution and biology are summarized.

Key words: Ukraine, Diptera, Tephritidae, gall inducers, new records.

Корнєєв С. В., Воловник С. В. і Корнєєв В. А. Перша знахідка *Tephritis hurvitz* (Diptera: Tephritidae) на материковій території України з нотатками про поширення та біологію. — *Tephritis hurvitz* Freidberg, 1981 є одним із небагатьох галотворювачів роду *Tephritis*, що індукують деформацію стебла під суцвіттями *Tragopogon* та *Scorzonera* (Asteraceae). Зустрічається в степах від східного Казахстану до Ізраїлю (Голанські висоти) та України. Раніше він був відомий тільки з Кримського півострова, але нещодавно виявлений на материковій Україні. Узагальнено відомості про поширення та біологію.

Ключові слова: Україна, Diptera, Tephritidae, галотворювачі, нові знахідки.

Freidberg (1981) described *T. hurvitz* based on a wide series of specimens from Israel (Golan Heights, Galilee), Cyprus, Turkey, Iran, and Qazaqstan (Shymkent). Later, Korneyev & Dirlbek (2001) recorded it from Syria, Iraq and Jordan; they also mentioned this species to occur in Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, but did not refer to any material. Korneyev (2003) recorded it from Crimean Peninsula (Ukraine). In this note, we list extensive collection material examined then by SVK for his PhD thesis, but also remained unpublished. Recently, SVV and VAK collected this species also in two localities the mainland Ukraine.

Tephritis hurvitz Freidberg, 1981 (Figs 1–5)

Freidberg, 1981; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989 (description, key); Korneyev & Dirlbek, 2001 (new records); Korneyev, 2003 (new records); Freidberg & Kütük, 2004 (key, new records); Korneyev & Nikelshparg, 2015 (new records); Mohamadzade Namin & Korneyev, 2018 (checklist); Korneyev et al. 2021 (new records).

Material examined. Armenia: Dilijan, 4.07.1931, 1 ♀ (V. Popov) (ZISP); **Iran:** Kohgiluyeh, pass near Sisakht, 30°52,29' N 51°31,26' E, h = 3300 m, 26.05.2014, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev) (SIZK); Qazvin, wetland at waterfall, 36°21,50' N 50°03,42' E, h = 1500 m, 7.06.2014, 2 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev) (SIZK); Kurdistan, 2 km W of Hossein Abad, 35°32,19' N 47°09,40' E, h = 1880 m, 13.06.2014, 1 ♂, 2 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev) (SIZK); East Azerbaijan Province: Dizmar Protected Area, Chichakli val., 38°40,50' N 46°32,05' E, h = 2215 m, 26.06.2014, 2 ♂ (S. & V. Korneyev) (SIZK); **Israel:** Mt. Hermon, 1600 m, 27.06.1977, ex stem gall on

Figs 1–5. *Tephritis hurvitzii*: 1 — specimens from Melitopol, 2 — male from Chernivtsi, 3 — galls under flower heads (Kyrgyzstan); 4 — same, larvae in dissected gall; 5 — empty puparia in a dissected gall, Melitopol.

Tragopogon longirostris, 1.07.1977, 1♀; 2.07.1977, 1♂ (A. Freidberg) (RMNH); 6.07.1977, 1♂, 1♀ (A. Freidberg) (MNKB) (paratypes); **Qazaqstan**: Talas Alatau, Aksu canyon, 20–21.08.1935, 1♀ (Shulpin) (ZISP); Aksu Djabagly Nature Reserve, 21.08.1964, 1♂; 10.09.1964, 1♀ (Fisechko) (SIZK); Saur Ridge, Karaungur River, 12.07.1965, 1♂ (Ponomarenko) (SIZK); Zhambyl Region. SW of Georgievka village, 26.05.1983, ex *Tragopogon capitatus* 13.06.1983, 5♂, 4♀; 18.06.1983, 27♂, 15♀ (Fedotova) (SIZK); Almaty, Medeo, 5.07.1990, 1♂ (Ermolenko) (SIZK); **Kyrgyzstan**: Mikhailovka, Ferghana Ridge, Kugart River valley, 16.05.1925, 1♀ (Th. Dobzhansky) (ZISP); Ferghana Ridge, Ak-Tau, 1500 m, 23.08.1928, 1♂ (N. Kuznetsov) (ZISP); **Russian Federation**: Saratov Region., N. Bannovka, 3.07.2003, 1♂ (V. Krivokhatsky & O. Ovchinnikova) (ZISP); Saratov (Volzhskiy District, Yubileyniy, Zashitnikov Otechestva St.), ex galls on *Tragopogon dubius*, coll. 4.08.2015, em. 17–20.08.2015, 1♂, 6♀ (Nikelshparg leg.) (Nikelshparg's pers. coll.); **Tadjikistan**: 40 km N Dushanbe, Ruydashat area, 3000 m, 22.07.1937, 1♂ (Gussakovskiy) (ZISP); Kvak area, Kondara canyon, 11.07.1977, 2♀ (Zlobin) (SIZK); Ganishou, 1700–2400 m, 15.06.1987, 1♂, 3♀ (Plushch) (SIZK); **Turkey**: Ankara, 04.1912, 2♂ (MHNP); Hakkari, above Suvarihalil, 2600 m, 11.08.1983, 1♂, 3♀ (K. Warneke) (RMNH); Patnos, 1600 m, 2.07.1985, 1♀ (C. J. Zwakhals) (RMNH); 8 km N Erzincan, 1750 m, H. & Th. v. Oorschot, H. v. d. Brink, 10.06.1988 (H. Wiering) (RMNH); **Turkmenistan**: Chandyr River valley, Sumbar, 23.04.1933, 1♀ (Ushinskiy) (ZISP); Khan-Takhta,

NW Ghissar Ridge, 3.09.1933, 2♂, 1♀ (Veltishchev) (ZISP); Kara-Kala: Parhai, 10.04.1992, 4♂, 2♀ (Kotenko) (SIZK); **Ukraine**: Crimea, Çufut Qale, 3 km E Bağçasaray, 29.04.1992, 2♂; Rybachye, Kanaka valley, 7–20.05.1993, 1♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK); Donetsk, Botanical Garden, 24.04.2014, 1♀ (Guglya) (SIZK); Zaporizha, Melitopol, 46.832561N, 35.354652E, 22.07.2021 1♂, 2♀ (Volovnik) (SIZK); Chernivtsi: Spaska, 23.07.2021, 1♂; Zavaloka, 23.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀ (V. Korneyev).

Host plants. *Tragopogon capitatus* S.A. Nikitin, *T. dubius* Scop., *T. longirostris* Bischoff ex Sch. Bip., *Scorzonera syriaca* Boiss. et Bl.

Distribution. Armenia, Cyprus, Greece, Israel, Iran, Iraq, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan (**first confirmed record**), Lebanon, Russian Federation, Syria, Tajikistan (**first record**), Turkey, Turkmenistan (**first record**), Ukraine. This species very probably occurs in Azerbaijan and Uzbekistan, but still not confirmed by any material; the paratype with label “Uzbekistan, Chim Gand” could be collected anywhere around Shymkent either in Kazaq or Uzbek territory.

Biology. Larvae after hatching from eggs in the flower head penetrate into hollow stem below and induce swelling

it into a gregarious gall (Fig. 3) containing 15–35 larvae (Fig. 4), which pupariate then inside stem and in June or July exit through the froth mass clot left inside of flower head leaving a gall full of empty black puparia (Fig. 5). Adults overwinter. Number of generations is unknown, but possibly one or two, depending on vegetation and climate.

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